

XVI SPANISH-PORTUGUESE SYMPOSIUM ON PLANT WATER RELATIONS NEW SOLUTIONS FOR ANCIENT CHALLENGES

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Magic beans or the miracle of tradition? Resilient bean landrace from Muniesa as a source of drought-adapted, seed-borne biofertilizers

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Abstract: Landrace beans from Muniesa, Teruel, Spain, have demonstrated remarkable adaptability to local drought conditions and harsh environments, often thriving in challenging soils. These landraces consistently yield high production rates even in years with extremely low rainfall. In fact, when compared to the Spanish Food Composition Database (BEDCA), these landraces exhibit similar nutritional profiles, while boasting even higher protein content. In contrast, modern varieties are typically bred for increased harvest volume, often at the expense of essential traits such as stress tolerance, defense against pathogens and pests, and the establishment of beneficial microbial associations. Beyond their distinct genetic makeup, we determined that the types of beneficial associations between these landraces and microorganisms play a pivotal role in their ability to thrive in adverse planting and growing conditions. In our study, we identified microbiota association patterns within the seeds of various commercial and landrace beans. These findings were then compared to discern meaningful insights. Our ultimate aim was to identify strains that can potentially be harnessed as bioinoculants in future applications, so we analyzed their features under stressing conditions as screening approach. Notably, certain strains isolated from Muniesa landraces, including *Bacillus bombysepticus* B1, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* B3, *Bacillus cereus* M1 and *Paenibacillus pabuli* M2, have been positively tested as biofertilizers and drought-tolerant enhancers for commercially grown beans sensitive to stressful conditions. The results were highly promising, demonstrating significant protection against stress in the early stages of development, which may enhance their performance in later phases. This approach not only deepened our understanding of the impact of the domestication process on microbial association patterns but also yielded a new set of bioinoculants capable of bolstering bean crops under water-deficient conditions. Finally, this serves as an exemplary model for how landraces can contribute to the revitalization of depopulated areas in Spain and Portugal, facilitating the restoration of local biodiversity and establishment of sustainable, high-value crops.

Keywords: seedborne microbiota, drought mitigation, bean landraces, legumes-microbiota interactions

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1. Introduction

The agricultural sector is facing increasing challenges, such as drought and high temperatures, which are negatively impacting production. In the case of legumes, these conditions can compromise biological nitrogen fixation by reducing the number of nodules, where this process occurs (Dovrat et al., 2018). These challenges are further compounded by the fact that breeding programs have primarily focused on production factors, rather than stress-tolerant traits (Singh and van der Knaap, 2022). Therefore, it is imperative to find treatments that can ensure early-stage development under restricted water regimes. Microbes are emerging as a promising alternative for enhancing plant tolerance to stress. It has been reported that the most effective treatments based on microorganisms are those that are isolated from the same environment and plant they are intended to be used with (Kumar et al., 2022). However, many commercial varieties of plants available today have limited interactions with beneficial microbiota due to the domestication breeding process (Gutierrez and Grillo, 2022). This can greatly limit the type and number of strains that can potentially serve as a stress-alleviating treatment. Interestingly, the solution may lie in the preservation of landraces, which are better adapted to harsh conditions. These landraces represent a middle stage between wild ancestors and modern varieties, and may preserve beneficial interactions that are worth exploring (Johnston-Monje and Raizada, 2011). Recently, there has been a description of the characterization of seed microbiota to improve the selection and efficiency of candidates for biotreatments, by adding a new layer of complexity. This approach includes parental selection of inherited strains and pre-adaptation to the plant species for future biotreatments (Nelson, 2018). In this sense, parental plants growing under adverse conditions tend to select more suitable strains to face such events. Studies have shown that this type of microbiota in legumes provides impressive results, reducing screening processes and enhancing the adequacy of future microbe-based products (Niza-Costa et al., 2022). The aim of the present study was to describe the seed microbiota from Muniesa (Teruel, Spain) landrace beans, which are known for their high production level under harsh soils and water-restrictive conditions, as candidates for enhancing the response and tolerance of commercial beans to water scarcity processes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Plant material and seedborne microbiota characterization

Landrace (Blanca, Pinta and Color de Caña) and commercial (Carrila, Verdina, Caparron, Amarella, Catarino and Canellini) beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) were provided by Casa Yus (Muniesa, Spain) and acquired in markets around Zaragoza (Spain), respectively. About 50 seeds were surface-sterilized with 70% ethanol for 5 minutes, and washed with sterile, double distilled water (Vílchez et al., 2021). They were then germinated in Magenta boxes in

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darkness at 25 °C, and then three 3-cm length roots were grounded, diluted in sterile NaCl 0.45% solution and dispersed in LB agar plates to quantify the culturable populations. Distinguishable colonies were isolated and pure cultures were identified by PCR amplification of the 16S rRNA gene, as previously optimized in our laboratory for seedborne microbiota (Niza-Costa et al., 2022). The core, resilient microbiota was described and the isolates were glycerol-preserved at -80 °C. The strains were evaluated under regular conditions and supplemented by 15% polyethylene glycol (PEG) as drought-mimicking agent. Thereafter, they were characterized as able to produce 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylate (ACC) deaminase, biofilm, auxins, antioxidants, proline and siderophores, as well as to fix nitrogen, and solubilize phosphate, calcium, silica, magnesium, zinc and potassium, as previously optimized and tested in our lab for high-throughput, spectrophotometric tests (Niza Costa et al., 2023). Finally, the colonization ratio of the candidates in the commercial variety ‘Carrila’, was assessed by *in vitro* tests, according to Vilchez and collaborators (Vilchez et al., 2021).

2.3 Evaluation of candidates as drought-tolerance enhancers in seedlings

The best candidates were prepared as liquid inoculants (10^8 colony forming units/mL in 0.45% NaCl solution) to treat 2-days-old seedlings in 0.5 L pots filled with turf and vermiculite (3:1, v:v). After treatment, irrigation regimes of 100% and 25% were applied (Vilchez et al., 2016). Then, 14 days after treatment (DAT), height, root length, dry weight (DW) and photosystem II quantum yield were evaluated (FluorPen FP110).

3. Results

The various bean varieties displayed diverse microbial profiles and persistent core microbiota, even among landrace varieties from the same region. The main component of the core microbiota across the varieties was Bacillaceae family strains (as depicted in Fig. 1). While some strains, such as *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Paenibacillus polymyxa*, were commonly isolated in most varieties, others were unique to specific varieties. For instance, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* and *Bacillus bombysepticus*, as well as *Paenibacillus pabuli*, were only isolated from the ‘Blanca’ and ‘Color de Caña’ landrace varieties, respectively, while *Priestia megaterium* was only detected in landrace varieties ‘Pinta’ and in commercial variety ‘Carrila.’ In contrast, strains such as *Bacillus atrophaeus* and *Bacillus anthracis* were restricted to commercial varieties.

We selected a series of strains, including *B. bombysepticus* B1, *Bacillus velezensis* B2, *B. amyloliquefaciens* B3, *B. subtilis* P1, *P. megaterium* P2, *B. cereus* P3, *P. polymyxa* P4, *B. cereus* M1, and *P. pabuli* M2, which were isolated from landrace varieties, but some also present in commercial varieties. We then evaluated their potential to benefit plants under stressful

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conditions, and our results indicated that all strains displayed noteworthy levels of the parameters we assessed. Among the most significant findings, we observed that the strains maintained their levels of auxins and biofilm production under 15% PEG treatment (Fig. 2a,b). Additionally, the P1 and P2 strains displayed notable growth in ACC medium under stress conditions (Fig. 2c), while the P3, B1, M1, and M2 strains stood out for their antioxidant production (Fig. 2d). On the other hand, proline production increased under stress for the P1 and M1 strains (Fig. 2e), where only P4 was able to maintain its nitrogen fixation level (Fig. 2f). Furthermore, all strains, except M1, were able to increase the amount of solubilized phosphorous under stress (Fig. 2g), and the same result was recorded for strains P1, B2, and B3 in the case of potassium solubilization (Fig. 2h). The production of siderophores increased under drought-mimicking conditions for strains B1, B2, B3, M1, and M2 (Fig. 2i). Lastly, the colonization ratio was consistent for most strains under stress conditions, but strains B3 and M1 were able to increase their colonization ratio (Fig. 2j). It should be noted that strains P1, B3, M1, and M2 were able to solubilize calcium, and P3, B1, B3, M1, and M2 were able to solubilize manganese, although these skills were not that consistently reported.

Figure 1. Characterization of the seedborne population in maize. The stacked columns chart shows the relative abundance of isolated strains in different landraces and commercial bean seeds.

Due to these results, we decided to perform biotreatment test with B1, B3, M1 and M2 in commercial 'Carrila' beans seedlings to evaluate drought-tolerance enhancing potential from landrace-isolated strains. They were chosen after stand out results in several test and/or consistency top performance for most of the tests previously reported. After 7 days of treatment, the early results indicate all treatments improved the size of the seedlings under full irrigation conditions (100%) respect to the control set, standing out the treatment with M1 and M2. In the case of water deprivation (25%), again, all treatments showed bigger and healthier seedlings, with the sets treated with M1 and B1 showing similar results respect to the non-stressing conditions.

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Figure 2. Strains characterization. The graph bars show the performance of the candidate strains in regular (blue) and stressing conditions (+15%PEG; green) for the production of auxin equivalents (a), biofilm structures (b), growth in ACC medium (c), production of antioxidants (d) and proline (e), fixation of nitrogen (f), solubilization of phosphate (g) and potassium (h), production of siderophores (i) and the colonization ratio (j). The * stands for significant difference at least $p < 0.05$ respect to regular conditions.

Figure 3. Inoculation effect on early-stage seedlings. The picture shows the phenotype registered 7 days after inoculations with the candidate strains under full irrigation (100%) and water deprivation (25%). Here 'Mock' stands for control set; 'M1', for *B. cereus* M1; 'M2', for *P. pabuli* M2; 'B1', for *B. bombysepticus* B2; and 'B3', for *B. amyloliquefaciens* B3.

4. Discussion

The study of seed microbial communities has the potential to introduce a novel approach for safeguarding plants and enhancing their performance under adverse circumstances. While additional research is necessary and the variability is considerable, the core microbiota we have identified in this study aligns with previous findings in the field and with

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other seed studies in legume plants. The significant presence of the Bacillaceae family, including *Bacillus*, *Paenibacillus*, and *Stenotrophomonas*, was also observed in the seeds of *Medicago sativa* and *Bituminaria bituminosa* wild plants (Niza-Costa et al., 2022). Notably, other studies have reported that this seed microbiota serves as a powerful biotreatment for legumes, exhibiting a higher proportion of beneficial strains compared to conventional sources (Laranjeira et al., 2022). Our study revealed that, in most instances, these characteristics were maintained by the strains under stressful conditions, which is advantageous for practical application and ensures the efficacy of biotreatments when water supply is uncertain or restricted. Here, the landrace varieties showed unique and shared strains, which could suggest the consequences of domestication on population interaction and heredity (Gutierrez and Grillo, 2022). However, further studies are required to establish a solid pattern.

The results of the main candidates *B. cereus* M1, *P. pabuli* M2 and *B. amyloliquefaciens* B3 indicates that seedborne isolated strains from Muniesa landraces were not only able to promote the growth in modern varieties, but also efficiently protect them against intense water deprivation. All these strains have been reported as beneficial bacteria for plants (mainly as biocontrollers), some even in legumes, but the specificity seems to be playing a role, as they were not frequently reported as biotreatment for beans (Kulkova, et al., 2023; Trinh et al., 2018; Mokrani et al., 2018). In the case of *B. bombysepticus* B2, as far as we know, this is the first reported case of beneficial effect on plants for this strain. These results open an interesting perspective to study further use of landrace sourced strains as new biotreatments for modern varieties of beans.

5. Conclusions

The microbial community within seeds exhibits significant diversity among different varieties, with some containing exclusive species. The microbial population present in landrace seeds was found to possess a number of characteristics with a notable performance, suggesting that seed microbiota possesses a promising potential for more effective biological treatments. All the strains improved the size of the seedlings in early stage, both under full irrigation and stressing conditions. The strain *B. cereus* M1 was especially consistent in both conditions. This is the first report of a *B. bombysepticus* as plant beneficial bacteria. Hence, seedborne isolated from Muniesa landraces showed to be an effective treatment enhancing modern varieties to resist the drought.

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